

DAAD Programme „Higher education cooperation with Jordan and Lebanon to support Syrian university staff”

Project profile

Title of the project:

German Jordanian Applied University Teaching (aut@gju.digi)

Name of the German university(ies):

Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences

Project Manager(s):

Prof. Dr. Anne Lequy

Partner country/countries:

Jordan

Partner university(ies):

German Jordanian University, Jordan

Brief description / project goals:

German Jordanian Applied University Teaching (aut@gju.digi) is a programme of further education anchored at the German Jordanian University (GJU) which creates a modular, sustainable and via Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences (HSMS) quality-assured structure for the further didactic qualification of Syrian academics. Jordanian and Lebanese teaching staff is simultaneously integrated in the didactic qualification at GJU. The programme is flanked by to be established specialised didactic working groups, which promote the further development of research and, above all, teaching. The modules, courses and offers are in detail:

1. The course aut.foundation-course@gju.digi teaches the basics of applied-oriented teaching in three modules, which are in turn divided into edu-units.
2. The certificate course aut.certificate@gju.digi builds on and extends the modules mentioned under point 1. by offering two further modules: "aut.coaching" and "aut.didactic-networks".
3. aut.conference@gju.digi provides the project with national and regional attention through an annual conference on specialised didactic topics as well as a platform for scientific exchange and the dissemination of gained knowledge and findings.
4. aut.structure@gju.digi envisages the establishment of a university didactics unit at GJU, which will cooperate internationally with that of the HSMS.

In connection with the to be established Digital Teaching Department and in accordance with the GJU's digitisation strategy, a centre of competence for higher education teaching of regional significance shall be created in Jordan through the project in the long-term, thus contributing to capacity building for the Syrian higher education system.

Links:

www.gju.edu.jo ; www.german-jordanian.org